

The Urdu Alphabet: A Confluence of Culture, History, and Phonetics in South Asian Linguistics

Author: Zafar | The Part-Time Poet

Affiliation: Kafila Live

Date: October, 13th 2024

Introduction:

The Urdu script is more than just a collection of letters—it is a living testament to centuries of linguistic evolution, cultural amalgamation, and poetic tradition. Emerging from the fusion of **Perso-Arabic**, **Sanskrit**, and **local dialects**, Urdu has grown into a language celebrated for its literary elegance and emotional depth. Each letter of the Urdu alphabet encapsulates not only a sound but also a rich tapestry of historical and cultural narratives that span empires, spiritual movements, and the daily lives of millions.

At its heart, the Urdu script is an intersection of art and science—its aesthetic flow complements its precise phonetic structure. This research aims to unravel the complexities of the **Urdu alphabet**, offering insights into its **historical development**, **phonetic precision**, and **cultural significance**, particularly in the realm of Urdu poetry, where language transcends mere communication to become a vehicle of profound expression. By bridging the gap between its **orthographic beauty** and **linguistic function**, this paper provides an essential guide for both scholars and learners eager to explore this vibrant language.

This paper explores the cultural, historical, and phonetic nuances of the Urdu alphabet, comparing each letter with its Hindi and English counterparts. By examining the roots of each character and its journey across languages, this research aims to demystify the script for learners, while celebrating its deep ties to Urdu poetry and literary traditions.

Background

The Urdu alphabet consists of 38 letters, each carrying its own phonetic value and connection to other languages like Arabic and Persian. However, these letters are more than just symbols; they reflect the cultural shifts and historical influences that have shaped the language. From Alif to Yay, each letter not only represents a sound but tells a story—whether it's about the historical evolution of Urdu as the language of poets and rulers, or its role in spiritual expression through words like "Allah" and "Ishq".

Historically, Urdu grew as a language of refinement in the courts of Mughal India, blending local dialects with Persian and Arabic influences. The richness of its poetry, literature, and philosophy gave Urdu a unique place in the world of linguistics. This article focuses on the alphabet's unique contributions, particularly in the realm of phonetics, as well as its literary symbolism.

Objectives of the Research:

1. **Cultural and Historical Context:** To delve into the historical evolution of the Urdu alphabet, tracing its roots from Perso-Arabic scripts and examining its adaptation in the Indian subcontinent.
2. **Phonetic Mapping and Comparisons:** To break down each letter, providing phonetic comparisons with Hindi and English to aid non-Urdu speakers, while discussing the subtle nuances in pronunciation and meaning.
3. **Linguistic and Poetic Symbolism:** To explore the deeper symbolic and poetic meaning attached to Urdu letters, showcasing their role in expressing complex emotions, spiritual ideas, and cultural values in Urdu poetry.
4. **Practical Learning Approach:** To offer a resource that not only introduces the technical aspects of Urdu letters but also presents them within real-world contexts—through common words, poetic verses, and historical references—making the alphabet accessible to learners.
5. To provide an accessible guide for non-Urdu speakers by breaking down the alphabet with phonetic equivalents in Hindi and English.
6. To explore the Linguistic significance of each letter, demonstrating its historical roots and symbolic meanings.
7. To bridge the gap between the technical study of letters and the emotional depth they carry in Urdu poetry and literature and to create a resource for learners that integrates linguistic theory with practical examples from everyday words, poetry, and expressions.

Expanding on the Research:

- ❖ In this paper, the Urdu alphabet is treated not just as a linguistic tool, but as a cultural artifact that carries the weight of history and literature. Each letter will be presented with its phonetic value, historical significance, and usage in daily life as well as in poetic contexts. Special emphasis will be placed on how Urdu letters, like Alif, Bay, and Jeem, are more than phonemes—they are the foundation stones of Urdu poetry, where sound and meaning converge to create expressions of love, loss, and spirituality.

- ❖ For example, the letter Alif (ا) is not only the first letter of the Urdu alphabet but symbolizes the unity of existence, often found in mystical poetry where it represents the divine. In contrast, letters like Bay (ب) and Jeem (ج) appear in everyday words but have deeper philosophical connotations when used in poetry, illustrating themes of human relationships, emotions, and life's complexities.

- ❖ By juxtaposing linguistic analysis with cultural and poetic elements, this paper provides an enriched understanding of the Urdu script—transforming it from a mere alphabet into a gateway for exploring the philosophical, artistic, and spiritual traditions of South Asia.

INDEX

ا ب پ ت ٹ ث

ج چ ح خ

د ڈ ذ ر ژ ز ژ

س ش ص ض

ط ظ ع غ ف ق

ک گ ل م ن ں

و ہ ہ ی ی ے

Alif

Alif (ا)

Historical Origin: Alif comes from the Phoenician letter Aleph, which originally depicted an ox's head (𐤀). This symbol evolved into a straight line in Arabic script to represent the primary sound "a" or a silent carrier for vowels.

Symbolism: Alif symbolizes the number one (1) in Arabic numerology, representing the unity of God (Tawhid). Its upright, simple line symbolizes purity and singularity, reflecting the belief in the absolute unity of existence. In Sufi philosophy, Alif represents the Divine, standing at the beginning of all creation, as it is also the first letter in Allah.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ALIF	Long "Ā"	अ, इ, उ, आ	Teacher Icon	

Sounds

Special Note:

ALIF is the most versatile letter. Do not be discouraged by the complexities described below. Most of the other letters are simpler.

ALIF can represent several different vowel sounds, depending on where it appears in a word. In the **middle** or **end** of a word, it always represents the long ā sound.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
shām	شام	शाम
dāl	دال	दाल
Deepā	دیپا	दीपा
jā	جا	जा

At the **beginning** of a word ALIF functions as a "silent carrier" for all the different vowel sounds. Any word that begins with a vowel sound **must** begin with a silent ALIF. We distinguish between **short** and **long** vowels:

Silent ALIF as a carrier for *short* vowels:

The three short vowels (“a”, “i”, and “u”) have no letters of their own. Diacritic marks (Ahrāb) above or below ALIF **may** be used to distinguish the three short vowel sounds, but these marks are usually omitted.

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
short “a” as in “about” (the optional diacritic mark is called “zabar”)	agar	اگر	अगर
short “i” as in “it” (the optional diacritic mark is called “zair”)	itnā	یتنا	इतना
short “u” as in “put” (the optional diacritic mark is called “pesh”)	utnā	اُتنا	उतना

Since the “zabar-zair-pesh” are almost always omitted, you will have to guess which sound to use based on the context of the word.

Silent ALIF as a carrier for *long vowels*:

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
long “a” as in “father” (the sign over ALIF is called “madd-zabar”: it cannot be omitted, and it used only at the beginning of a word)	āsmān	آسمان	आसमान
like the “e” in “evil”	īmān	ایمان	ईमान
like the “a” in “ache”	ek	ایک	एक
like the “a” in “asset”	aisā	ایسا	ऐसा
like the “o” in “over”	os	اوس	ओस
like the “aw” in “awesome”	aur	اور	और
like the “oo” in “oops”	ūpar	اوپر	ऊपर

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
--	-------	--------	---------	----------

Basic Forms	ل	Use final	Use detached	ا
In Context	جانا	Use Final	Use Detached	اور
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Connections

ALIF is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus ALIF has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When ALIF appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	agar	اگر
When ALIF appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	dām	دام
When ALIF appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its final form.	tāj	تاج
ALIF with the madd-zabbar sign appears only at the beginning of a word.	āj	آج

ALIF has special “mashed” connecting forms with the following letters:

ک + ا = کا

گ + ا = گا

ل + ا = لا

Additional Examples of Alif

Final	Detached
چار	اچار
اچھا	اچھا
کھانا	میرا
ناچنا	آرام
	اونٹ

BAY ب

Baa (ب)

- Historical Origin: Baa evolved from the Phoenician Bet, which depicted a house (🏠). Over time, its shape was simplified, and in Arabic, the single dot below helps distinguish it from other similar letters.
- Symbolism: Baa is linked to the idea of beginnings and structure, just as a house provides structure and shelter. It is the first letter in Bismillah (In the name of God), giving it immense significance in Islamic texts. Its open shape, like a container, represents receptivity or welcoming.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ب	BAY	English "B"	ब	Teacher Icon

Sounds

BAY sounds like the English "b".

Connections

BAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	بب	ببب	با	ب
In Context	كب	سبزی	بہت	اب
Write in Context	(animation)	(animation)	(animation)	(animation)

BAY is a member of the "point system" family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family.

Other	Three Dots	Two Dots	One Dot	
Retroflex TAY	SAY	TAY	NOON	
ٹ	ٹ	ت	ن	Above

	ب	ے ای	ب	Below
	PAY	YAY (Dots only in initial & medial forms)	BAY	

Variations

For aesthetic reasons, the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are 3 examples of the three initial shapes of

ب:

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

In some cases the cusp for medial ب gets smoothed out.

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

کبھی قبر

Examples:

Aspirations

BAY can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (آ).

In this combination, the “b” sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated BAY: you should feel a puff of air:

بھ	भ
----	---

Examples

بھی	bhee	भी
کبھی	kabhee	कभी
سبھی	sabhee	सभी

بھوت	bhoot	भूत
بھوک	bhook	भूख

Additional Examples of ب

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
قرب	قبر	بینگن	اب
غریب		بیلن	عرب
مطلب	کبیر	بس	ادب
سبب		بیوی	محبوب
قطب مینار		بات	جناب
		بنانا	جواب

PAY پ

Pay (پ):

- **Sound:** The "p" sound was missing in Arabic, which only has **Baa (ب)** for the "b" sound. Persian added **Pay** by placing three dots beneath **Baa**.
- **Usage in Persian and Urdu:** The sound "p" is widespread in Persian words like "پدر" (Pedar, father) and "پای" (Pāy, foot). Similarly, in Urdu, **Pay** is found in common words like "پانی" (Pānī, water).
- **Symbolism:** While Arabic has its symbolic roots tied to the form of letters, **Pay**, being a later addition, generally symbolizes practicality and adaptability. Its form, based on **Baa**, visually continues the theme of "containment" or grounding, aligning with foundational concepts like family (e.g., father, foot).

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
پ	PAY	English "P"	प	Teacher Icon

Sounds

PAY Sounds like the English "p" but without an aspiration. English speakers tend to aspirate "p". Pronounce "p" with your hand in front of your mouth: you should not feel any puff of air.

Hindi equivalent: प

Connections

PAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	پ	سپب	پہت	پ
In-Context	سپ	سپنا	پیسے	آپ
Write-In Context	animation	animation	animation	animation

PAY is a member of the "point system" family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family.

Other	Three Dots	Two Dots	One Dot	
Retroflex TAY	SAY	TAY	NOON	
ٹ	ٹ	ت	ن	Above
	پ	ے / ی	ب	Below
	PAY	YAY (Dots only in initial & medial forms)	BAY	

Variations

For aesthetic reasons, the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are 3 examples of the three initial shapes of پ:

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

پہاڑ	واپس	پڑھنا
------	------	-------

پہاڑ	واپس	پڑھنا
------	------	-------

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

پتھر

In some cases the cusp for medial پ gets smoothed out.

Example:

Aspirations

PAY can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (آ).

In this combination, the “p” sound does include a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated PAY: now you should feel a puff of air.

پہ	پا
----	----

Examples

پھل		phal	फल
پھول		phool	फूल
پھر		phir	फिर

Additional Examples of پ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
سانپ	دیپا	پانچ	دھوپ
میپ		پیار	ناپ
		پوری	
		پولیس	
		اپنا	
		اوپر	

TAY ت

Taa (ت)

- **Historical Origin:** The letter Taa evolved from the Phoenician Taw (𐤕), which symbolized a mark or a cross. In Arabic, the shape took a more rounded form with two distinguishing dots.
- **Symbolism:** The dual dots in Taa are often seen to symbolize duality—the dual aspects of life such as light and dark, good and evil. The letter is associated with action and distinction, separating things into categories, which is reflected in words related to teaching and defining.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ت	TAY	~ English “T”	त	Teacher Icon

Sounds

TAY is somewhat different from the English “t” sound. Pronounce “t” with the tongue forward, touching the back of the teeth. Look in the mirror when you pronounce TAY. You should be able to see your tongue. TAY is often called “dental t”. It is similar to the English sound “th” as in “then” or “the” but with more pressure of the tongue on the teeth. TAY should not be aspirated: if you put your palm in front of your mouth you should not feel any puff of air when pronouncing TAY. (But see “Aspiration” below).

There is another letter with the dental “t” sound in Urdu: TOE (ط). You must learn when to use TAY and when to use TOE. They are not interchangeable.

Connections

TAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ت	تا	تی	ت
In-Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write-In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

TAY is a member of the “point system” family. The letters in this family consist of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family.

Other	Three Dots	Two Dots	One Dot	
Retroflex TAY	SAY	TAY	NOON	
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	Above
	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	Below
	PAY	YAY (Dots only in initial & medial forms)	BAY	

Variations

For aesthetic reasons, the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are 3 examples of the three initial shapes of TAY:

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
---------	---------	---------

In some cases the cusp for medial ت gets smoothed out.

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

fill-in

Example:

Aspirations

TAY can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (آ).

In this combination, the “dental t” sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated TAY: you should feel a puff of air:

Additional Examples of ت

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
-------	--------	---------	----------

fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Retroflex TAY

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ٹ	Retroflex TAY	~ English "T"	ट	Teacher Icon

Sounds

Retroflex TAY is somewhat different from the English "t" sound. Pronounce "t" with tongue pulled back in your mouth, touching the ride of your palate. Look in the mirror when you pronounce Retroflex TAY. You should NOT be able to see your tongue. Be careful not to "aspirate" Retroflex TAY. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce this letter: you should NOT feel any puff of air. But see "Aspiration" below.

Retroflex TAY is used to transliterate the English "t" sound, although it is actually quite different. Use Retroflex TAY whenever you write an English word in Urdu that contains "t".

Hindi Equivalent: ट

Connections

Retroflex TAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ٹ	بٹن	اٹر	ٹ
In-Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write-In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Retroflex TAY is a member of the "point system" family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family.

Other	Three Dots	Two Dots	One Dot	
Retroflex TAY	SAY	TAY	NOON	
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	Above

	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	Below
	PAY	YAY (Dots only in initial & medial forms)	BAY	

Variations

For aesthetic reasons, the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are 3 examples of the three initial shapes of Retroflex TAY:

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
---------	---------	---------

In some cases the cusp for medial ٹ gets smoothed out.

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

fill-in

Examples:

Aspirations

Retroflex TAY can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (ہ).

In this combination, Retroflex TAY does include a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce aspirated retroflex TAY: now you should feel a puff of air:

fill-in	ہ
---------	---

Examples

fill-in	theek	ठीक
fill-in	meethā	मीठा
fill-in	baithnā	बैठना

fill-in	Thand	ٹھنڈ
---------	-------	------

Additional Examples of ٹھ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

SAY

Thaa (ث)

- Historical Origin: Thaa also developed from Phoenician scripts but was modified in Arabic by the addition of three dots.
- Symbolism: Thaa is less common but carries connotations of knowledge and clarity, perhaps because of the sharp sound and the three dots, which could be interpreted as representing clarity in all directions or dimensions.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ث	SAY	English "S"	स	Teacher Icon

Sounds

SAY sounds like the English "s". There are two other letters that sound like "s" in Urdu: SEEN (س) and SWĀD (ص). They are not interchangeable: you must learn which words use which letter. SEEN is the most common, SWĀD is next most common, and SAY is quite rare.

Connections

SAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ث	مٹا	اٹر	ٹ
In-Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write-In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

SAY is a member of the "point system" family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family.

Other	Three Dots	Two Dots	One Dot	
Retroflex TAY	SAY	TAY	NOON	
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	Above

	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	Below
	PAY	YAY (Dots only in initial & medial forms)	BAY	

Variations

For aesthetic reasons, the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are 3 examples of the three initial shapes of ث:

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
---------	---------	---------

In some cases the cusp for medial ث gets smoothed out.

(If image is incorrect, replace with following code and fill-in urdu letters)

fill-in

Example:

Additional Examples of ث

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

JEEM ج

Jeem (ج)

- **Historical Origin:** Jeem derives from Phoenician Gimel (𐤂), originally symbolizing a camel or a throwing stick. Its shape evolved into the hook-like form in Arabic, with a distinguishing dot.
- **Symbolism:** Jeem symbolizes journeys or transitions, much like its origin as a camel, which was used for transportation. It also symbolizes beauty and grace, as it starts words like Jannah (paradise) and Jamal (beauty). The closed bottom of the letter can be seen as enclosing something precious or valuable.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent
ج	JEEM	ज

Sounds

JEEM sounds exactly like English “j”. It is NOT the French, German, or Spanish “j”.

Connections

JEEM can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	بیج	گجر	جا	ج
In Context	بیج	گجرات	جانا	آج
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Aspirations

JEEM can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (ہ).

In this combination, the “j” sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated JEEM: you should feel a puff of air:

Examples

مجھے	mujhe	मुझे
جھوٹ	jhūt	झूठ (note that the final letter is aspirated in Hindi but not in Urdu)
جھیل	jheel	झील

Additional Examples of ج

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
رنج	مجھے	جی	راج
جج	لیجیے	جو	تاج
	بھجنا	جادو	سورج
		گاجر	
		جنگل	

Che (چ):

- **Historical Origin:** **Che (چ)** was created by modifying **Jeem (ج)**, a letter that produces a "j" sound in Arabic. In Persian and Urdu, the "ch" sound (as in "church") was common, so **Che** was introduced with three dots above **Jeem**.
- **Usage in Persian and Urdu:** **Che** is essential for words like "چشم" (Chashm, meaning "eye") in Persian or "چائے" (Chāy, meaning "tea") in Urdu. The letter appears frequently in both languages.
- **Symbolism:** **Che**, derived from **Jeem**, carries connotations of connection and nurturing, as its original form in **Jeem** links to words like **Jannah** (paradise). **Che's** extension to the "ch" sound widens this idea, symbolizing protection and sustenance (as in "eye" or "nurturing tea").

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
چ	CHAY	च	Teacher Icon

Sounds

CHAY sounds exactly like English "ch" in "church". It is NOT the French or German "ch".

Connections

CHAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	سچ	بیچنا	چو	چ
In Context	سچ	بیچنا	چور	مرچ
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Aspirations

CHAY can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (ہ).

In this combination, the "ch" sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated CHAY: you should feel a puff of air:

Examples

چہے	chhai	چھہ
چھوٹا	chhoTā	چھوٹا
اچھا	achhā	اچھا

Additional Examples of چھ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
پانچ	چچا	چار	ناچ
بیچ	سچا	چاہنا	خرچ
لاچ	بچانا	اچار	سوچ
کانچ		چاول	
		چکلا	

ARABIC HAY ح

Haa (ح)

- Historical Origin: The Arabic Haa originates from Proto-Semitic Heth. It has retained a similar "h" sound across many Semitic languages, though the shape evolved into the current Arabic form.
- Symbolism: Haa is often seen as representing breath or spirit, as the soft "h" sound is the sound of breath. In mystical traditions, it can symbolize the hidden or invisible nature of divine reality, as it begins words like Haq (truth) and Hawa (desire).

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ح	BADI HAY (Arabic HAY)	ह	Teacher Icon

Sounds

ARABIC HAY sounds exactly like English “h”.

Arabic HAY (BADI HAY) is one of TWO “h” sounds in Urdu. We call ح the Arabic HAY (or Badi HAY) to distinguish it from ه which is called HINDI HAY (or CHHOTI HAY). Both sound the same but they are not interchangeable. You must learn when to use each one.

Connections

ARABIC HAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	صبح	محل	حنا	ح
In Context	صبح	محل	حنا	روح
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Additional Examples of ح

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
صحیح	صحیح	روحی	مصباح

فتح	صحت	حق	صلاح
مسیح	محبوب	حُقَّہ	طرح
کانچ	مُحَبَّت	حلوه	
	محسوس	حرام	
		حد	
		حلال	
		حور	
		حج	

Khaa (خ)

- Historical Origin: Khaa developed from Proto-Semitic Heth but evolved a harder, more guttural sound with the addition of the dot above.
- Symbolism: The strong, rough sound of Khaa symbolizes difficulty or challenge, such as in words like Khawf (fear). The letter is often associated with the notion of overcoming adversity.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
خ	KHAY	ख़	Teacher Icon

Sounds

KHAY sounds like the German or Scottish “ch”. It is similar to “h” but with more friction in the throat. KHAY must NEVER be confused with aspirated “k” sound represented in Urdu by ک and in Hindi by ख़ (without dot below).

Connections

KHAY can connect from both sides. Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	بطخ	مخمل	خر	خ
In Context	بطخ	مخمل	خر پدنا	شاه رُخ
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Additional Examples of خ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
تاریخ	شخص	خُدا	سوراخ
نسخ	فخر	خاندان	سُرخ
چیخ	تخت	خط	شاخ

شیخ	سخت	خاموش	
	نخرہ	خبر	
		خون	
		خرگوش	

DĀL د

Daal (-)

- Historical Origin: Daal evolved from the Phoenician Dalet (ד), which represented a door. The letter took on a simpler form in Arabic.
- Symbolism: Daal represents opening or passage, much like a door. It often symbolizes transitions or gateways, whether literal or metaphorical.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
د	DĀL	द	Teacher Icon

Sounds

DĀL is a “dental D”. It is somewhat different from the English “D” sound. Pronounce “D” with your tongue forward, touching your teeth. It is very close to a hard “th” sound, as in the English word “that”. Look in the mirror when you pronounce DĀL. You should be able to see the tip of your tongue under your teeth.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	مسجد	Use Final	Use Detached	د
In Context	مسجد	Use Final	Use Detached	دوکان
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Note that final DĀL looks a lot like detached RAY, but you won’t confuse the two because final DĀL is always connected to the preceding letter and detached RAY is never connected to the preceding letter.

Connections

DĀL is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus DĀL has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When DĀL appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	دور	dūr
When DĀL appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	أردو	Urdū

When DĀL appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its **final** form.

مندر

mandir

Note that final DĀL looks like a lot like detached Ray. But you won't confuse the two because final DĀL is **always** connected to the preceding letter, and detached Ray is **never** connected to the preceding letter. Also, final RAY looks quite different from detached RAY. This is true for all members of the DĀL and RAY families.

Aspiration

DAL can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (ہ).

In this combination, the DĀL sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce it: you should feel a puff of air.

دھ	ڈھ
----	----

Examples

دھنیواد	dhanyavād	धन्यवाद
بندھن	bandhan	बंधन
أدھر	udhar	उधर

Additional Examples of د

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
بندر			دام
ہندی			دروازہ
بعد			دل
خریدنا			دو
جلدی			دیکھنا
عید			دس

Retroflex DĀL

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ڈ	Retroflex DĀL	ड़	Teacher Icon

Sounds

Retroflex DĀL is somewhat different from the English “D” sound. Pronounce “D” with your tongue pulled back in your mouth, touching the ridge on your hard palate. Look in the the mirror when you pronounce Retroflex DĀL. You should NOT be able to see your tongue.

Retroflex DĀL is used to transliterate the English “D” sound into Urdu, although it is actually quite different. Use Retroflex DĀL whenever you write an English word in Urdu that contains a “D”.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	انڈیا	Use Final	Use Detached	ڈ
In Context	انڈیا	Use Final	Use Detached	ڈر
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Note that final Retroflex DĀL looks a lot like detached Retroflex RAY, but you won’t confuse the two because final Retro DĀL is always connected to the preceding letter and detached Retro RAY is never connected to the preceding letter.

Connections

Retroflex DĀL is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus Retroflex DĀL has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When Retroflex DĀL appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	ڈاکٹر	doctor
When Retroflex DĀL appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	روڈ	road
When Retroflex DĀL appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its final form.	بڈ	bud

Aspirations

Retroflex DĀL can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (ہ).

In this combination, the Retroflex DĀL sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated CHAY: you should feel a puff of air:

ڈھ	ڙھ
----	----

Examples

ڈھائی	Dhāee	ڙاڙي
ڈھابا	Dhābā	ڙاڙا
ڈھونڈھنا	DhūnDhnā	ڙھونڙھنا

Additional Examples of ڈھ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
ٹھنڈ			ڈالنا
انڈھ			ڈرنا
بانڈی			ڈھول
گھمنڈ			ڈبہ

ذ ZĀL

Dhaal (ذ)

- Historical Origin: Dhaal shares a similar origin with Daal but was distinguished by the addition of a dot. It corresponds to the Phoenician letter Zayin.
- Symbolism: The sound and the dot suggest precision or pointing out, as it often signifies emphasis in words where the letter appears.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ذ	ZĀL	ज़	Teacher Icon

Sounds

ZĀL sounds like the English “z”.

ZĀL is one of the Urdu letters for the “z” sound. The other letters for the “z” sound are: ZAY (ز), ZWĀD (ض), and ZOE (ظ). You must learn which one to use. They are not interchangeable.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ذ	Use Final	Use Detached	ذ
In Context	نذیک	Use Final	Use Detached	ذرا
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Connections

ZĀL is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus DĀL has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When ZĀL appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	ذرا	zarā
When ZĀL appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	اذان	azān

When ZĀL appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its **final** form.

جذبات

jazbāt

Note that final ZĀL looks a lot like detached ZAY, but you won't confuse the two because final ZĀL is always connected to the preceding letter and detached ZAY is never connected to the preceding letter.

Additional Examples of ذ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
جذ			ذلیل
مغذ			ذوجہ

RAY

Raa (ر)

- **Historical Origin:** Raa comes from the Phoenician Resh (𐤓), meaning head. The shape originally resembled a profile of a head but was simplified in Arabic.
- **Symbolism:** Raa is associated with motion or action, as it begins words like Rihla (journey) or Rahma (mercy). It reflects the idea of movement, just as the letter's curved form suggests forward motion.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ر	RAY	र	Teacher Icon

Sounds

RAY is rolled once quickly like Spanish “r”.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	جر	Use Final	Use Detached	ر
In Context	گاجر	Use Final	Use Detached	روحی
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Connections

RAY is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus RAY has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When RAY appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	روحی	roohi
When RAY appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	درد	dard
When RAY appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its final form.	سردی	sardī

Note that final DĀL looks a lot like detached RAY. But you won't confuse the two because final DĀL is always connected to the preceding letter, and detached RAY is never connected to the preceding

letter. Also, final RAY looks very different from detached RAY. This is true for all members of the DĀL and RAY families.

Additional Examples of ر

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
ٹمائے			چار
شہر			اور
مگر			روپے
خریدنا			چور
کرنا			بخار
نوکری			کار

Retroflex RAY

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ڑ	Retroflex RAY	ड़	Teacher Icon

Sounds

Retroflex RAY is flapped once quickly, but backwards with your tongue curled back in your mouth and then flapped forward toward your teeth. At first it may feel like you are pronouncing “R” and “L” at the same time.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ڪڙ	Use Final	Use Detached	ڑ
In Context	ڪڙا	Use Final	Use Detached	چوڙی
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Connections

Retroflex Flap RAY is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus Retroflex Flap RAY has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

Retroflex RAY never appears at the beginning of a word.		
When Retroflex RAY appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	دوڑ	dauR
When Retroflex Flap RAY appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its final form.	لڑکی	laRkee

Note that final Retroflex DĀL looks a lot like detached Retroflex RAY, but you won't confuse the two because final Retro DĀL is always connected to the preceding letter and detached Retro RAY is never connected to the preceding letter.

Aspirations

Retroflex RAY can be aspirated by the addition of the letter DO CHASHMI HAY (ھ).

In this combination, the Retroflex DĀL sound includes a distinct puff of air. Put your palm in front of your mouth when you pronounce Aspirated CHAY: you should feel a puff of air:

ڑھ	ڙھ
----	----

Examples

پڑھنا	paRhnā	पढ़ना
ڈیڑھ	DeRh	डेढ़
ساڑھے	sāRhay	साढ़े

Additional Examples of ڑھ

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
لڑکا			ساڑی
لڑکی			چوڑیاں
بڑا			گھوڑا
کپڑے			جاڑا

ZAY ز

Zaa (ز)

- Historical Origin: Derived from Phoenician Zayin (𐤆), Zaa maintained a "z" sound through many languages.
- Symbolism: Zaa is sharp and energetic, symbolizing vitality or zest. It represents something swift or piercing, much like the sound itself.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ز	ZAY	ज़	Teacher Icon

Sounds

ZAY sounds like the English "z". ZAY is one of the four letters that sound like "z".

The other letters for the "z" sound are: ZĀL (ذ), ZWĀD (ض), and ZOE (ظ). You must learn when to use each one. They are not interchangeable.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	چیز	Use Final	Use Detached	ز
In Context	چیز	Use Final	Use Detached	بازار
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Connections

ZAY is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus ZAY has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When ZAY appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	زندگی	zindagee
When ZAY appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	بازار	bāzār
When ZAY appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its final form.	چیز	cheez

Note that final ZĀL looks a lot like detached ZAY, but you won't confuse the two because final ZĀL is always connected to the preceding letter and detached ZAY is never connected to the preceding letter.

Additional Examples of ز

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
سبزی			روز
تیز			زور
میز			راز
تمیز			زمین

ZHAY

Zhe (ژ):

- **Historical Origin:** **Zhe (ژ)** was borrowed from **Persian** to represent the "zh" sound (as in the French "J" or the "s" in "measure"). This sound doesn't exist in Arabic. The letter was created by adding a single dot to **Zay (ز)**.
- **Usage in Persian and Urdu:** **Zhe** is found mostly in borrowed words from Persian, such as "ژاله" (Zhāleh, meaning "dew") or "ژاژ" (Zhāzh, meaning "nonsense"). In Urdu, it appears in borrowed words like "ژولیدہ" (Zhūlēdah, meaning "disheveled").
- **Symbolism:** **Zhe** represents refinement and smoothness due to its soft, flowing sound. Its unique presence highlights how Persian influenced the flow and sound of the language.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ژ	ZHAY	None	Teacher Icon

Sounds

ZHAY sounds like the French "j" or like the "s" in "confusion" or "division". ZHAY is only used in words borrowed from other languages like Persian or English.

Forms

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	مژ	Use Final	Use Detached	ژ
In Context	مژگان	Use Final	Use Detached	اژدہا
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Connections

ZHAY is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus ZHAY has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When ZHAY appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	ژاژ	zhāzh
When ZHAY appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	اژدہا	azhdahā

When ZHAY appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its **final** form.

مژگان

mizhgān

SEEN س

Seen (س)

- Historical Origin: Seen comes from Phoenician Shin (𐤑), which symbolized teeth or a sharp object.
- Symbolism: Seen is often seen as representing wisdom or knowledge, given that it begins the word SIRR (secret). Its smooth, flowing shape could be seen to symbolize the continuous flow of knowledge.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
س	SEEN	स	Teacher Icon

Sounds

SEEN sounds like the English “s”.

SEEN is one of three “s” sounds in Urdu. The others are SWĀD (ص) and SAY (ث). They are not interchangeable. You must learn when to use each one.

Forms

SEEN can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	بس	مسجد	سنترہ	س
In Context	بس	مسجد	سنترہ	دس
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Variations

SEEN has a “stretched” variation that is often encountered when you find two SEENs in succession. The “stretched” form may also be used for calligraphic purposes. Some fonts produce the stretched version automatically.

سسنا

Additional Examples of س

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
بیس	کیسا	ساڑی	اُس
جس	نمستے	سبزی	پاس
لا ماچس	پیسے	سیکھنا	پچاس

SHEEN ش

Sheen (ش)

- Historical Origin: Sheen shares the same origin as Seen but is distinguished by three dots above.
- Symbolism: Sheen symbolizes something bright or illuminating, such as in words like Shams (sun). The dots add an extra layer of emphasis or intensity.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ش	SHEEN	श/ष	Teacher Icon

Sounds

SHEEN sounds like the English “sh”.

Forms

SHEEN can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	دیش	مشہو	شا	ش
In Context	دیش	مشہور	شام	خوش
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Variations

SHEEN has a “stretched” variation that is often encountered when you find two SHEENs in succession. The “stretched” form may also be used for calligraphic purposes. Some fonts produce the stretched version automatically.

کوشش

Additional Examples of ش

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
پیش کش	جشن	شاه رُخ	کاش
مالش	چشمہ	شہر	تلاش
خوابش	مشین	شور	خرگوش
لِیش	لکشمی	آشرم	شاباش

ص SWĀD

Saad (ص)

- Historical Origin: Saad comes from Phoenician Tsade (𐤓), which originally symbolized a hook or a tool.
- Symbolism: Saad represents strength and restraint, reflected in its hard, emphatic sound. It often starts words related to righteousness or justice, like Sabr (patience) or Salaam (peace).

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ص	SWĀD	स	Teacher Icon

Sounds

SWĀD sounds like the English “s”.

SWĀD is one of three “s” sounds in Urdu. The others are SEEN (ص) and SAY (ث). They are not interchangeable. You must learn when to use each one.

Forms

SWĀD can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	شخص	فیصلہ	صا	ص
In Context	شخص	فیصلہ	صاف	خاص
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Additional Examples of ص

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
خالص	تصویر	صبح	خلوص
رقص	قِصَّہ	صرف	
	عُصَّہ	صائِن	

ض ZWĀD

Daad (ض)

- Historical Origin: Daad also originates from the same family as Saad but carries a stronger, emphatic sound.
- Symbolism: Daad is unique to Arabic (known as the language of Daad) and symbolizes uniqueness or distinction.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ض	ZWĀD	ज़	Teacher Icon

Sounds

ZWĀD sounds like the English “z”.

ZWĀD is one of the Urdu letters for the “z” sound. The other letters for the “z” sound are: ZĀL (ذ), ZAY (ز), and ZOE (ظ). They are not interchangeable. You must learn when to use each one.

Forms

ZWĀD can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	يض	غضب	ضر	ض
In Context	مريض	غضب	ضرور	قرض
Write in Context	fill-in			fill-in

Additional Examples of ض

Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
محض	مضبوط	ضد	فرض
فيض	فضول	ضمير	مرض

TOE ط

Taa (ط)

- Historical Origin: Taa also evolved from Phoenician Taw, but this version has an emphatic quality, distinguished from the regular Taa (ت).
- Symbolism: The emphatic Taa often represents determination or force, as seen in words like Tareeq (path).

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ط	ط	ط	ط

Sounds

TOE is another “dental t”, pronounced exactly the same as TAY (ت).

Hindi equivalent: त

There are two sounds for “dental t”: TAY (ت) and TOE (ط). They are not interchangeable. You must learn when to use each one.

Connections

TOE can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

ZOE ظ

Zaa (ظ)

- Historical Origin: Zaa comes from Phoenician Zayin, but like Taa, it is an emphatic version.
- Symbolism: Zaa symbolizes victory, emphasis or magnification, indicating something of importance.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ظ	ظ	ظ	ظ

Sounds

ZOE sounds like English “z”.

Hindi equivalent: ज्ञ

ZOE is one of the Urdu letters for the “z” sound. The other letters for the “z” sound are: ZĀL (ذ), ZWĀD (ض), and ZAY (ز). You must learn when to use each one. They are not interchangeable.

Connections

ZOE can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

‘AIN ع

Ayn (ع)

Historical Origin: As mentioned earlier, Ayn represents an eye and retains its original meaning from the Proto-Sinaitic script.

Symbolism: Ayn symbolizes insight or spiritual vision. In mysticism, it is associated with seeing beyond the physical world into deeper spiritual truths.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ع	ع	ع	ع

Sounds

‘AIN is a rare letter found mainly in words borrowed from Arabic, in which it represents a “glottal stop”. In Urdu its sound and function are essentially the same as ALIF’s. It is not, however, interchangeable with ALIF. You will need to learn which words are spelled with ‘AIN (ع) and which are spelled with ALIF (ا).

No Hindi equivalent.

‘AIN is usually transliterated with an apostrophe.

At the beginning of a word ‘AIN can carry any of the three short vowels:

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
“a” as in “about”	‘arab	عرب	अरब
“i” as in “inner”	‘izzat	عزت	इज़त
“u” as in “put”	‘urs	عرس	उर्स

At the beginning of a word ‘AIN is silent when followed by another vowel letter:

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
silent	‘ām	عام	आम
silent	‘aurat	عورت	औरत

In the middle or end of any word, ‘AIN is a wild card: it can represent almost any vowel sound or the consonant “y”.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
ba'ad	بعد	बाद
sho'lay	شعلے	शोले
shama'	شمع	शमा
shāyar	شاعر	शायर

Connections

'AIN can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

GHAIN غ

Ghayn (غ)

Historical Origin: Ghayn is a modified version of Ayn, with the addition of a dot.

Symbolism: Ghayn often symbolizes something hidden or veiled, reflected in its guttural sound. It appears in words like Ghayb (the unseen).

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ع	ع	ع	ع

Sounds

GHAIN sounds like the French or German “r”. Constrict the back of your throat but without closing off the air completely. Allow the air to pass through while you pronounce this letter. It is like a gentle gargling sound.

Hindi equivalent: र

GHAIN must never be confused with the hard “g” sound represented in Urdu by گ and in Hindi by ग without the dot below.

Connections

GHAIN can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

FAY ف

Faa (ف)

- Historical Origin: Faa evolved from Phoenician Pe, symbolizing a mouth.
- Symbolism: The letter is connected with speech or expression, reflecting its role as a voiced sound.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ف	ف	ف	ف

Sounds

FAY sounds like the English “f”.

Hindi equivalent: फ

FAY must never be confused with the aspirated “p” sound represented by پيچ and in Hindi by फ़ (without the dot below).

Connections

FAY can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

QĀF ق

Qaaf (ق)

- Historical Origin: Qaaf evolved from Phoenician Qoph, which symbolized a circle or the back of the head.
- Symbolism: Qaaf often represents something deep or hidden, especially in Sufi thought, where it is tied to spiritual depth.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ق	ف	ف	ق

Sounds

QĀF is pronounced by closing the very back of the throat, further back than for “k”.

Hindi equivalent: क

Do not confuse QĀF (ق) with the normal “k” sound represented in Urdu by KĀF (ك) and in Hindi by क (without the dot below). Try to distinguish between QĀF (ق) and KĀF (ك) in your pronunciation. Many Punjabi Urdu speakers pronounce QĀF (ق) the same as KĀF (ك) however.

Connections

QĀF can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

KĀF ك

Kaaf (ك)

- Historical Origin: Derived from the Phoenician Kaph, which symbolized the palm of the hand.
- Symbolism: Kaaf symbolizes both grasping or holding and its shape suggests openness or receptiveness.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ك	ك	ك	ك

Sounds

KĀF is the same as English “k”.

Hindi equivalent: क

Connections

KĀF can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**. The little squiggle over the tail of the letter is not normally written in handwriting.

KĀF has special combination forms with ALIF and LĀM:

ا + ك =	Hindi equivalent: का
ك = ل + ك	Hindi equivalent: कल or कला

Remember that nothing can connect after ALIF so ا is also a breaker. On the other hand ل is not a breaker because its final element is ل.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
kām	کام	काम
kal	کل	कल
muskān	مسکراہٹ	मुस्कान
takleef	مسئلہ	तकलीफ

گ GĀF

Gaf (گ):

- **Historical Origin:** **Gaf** (گ), like **Pay**, was adapted from the Arabic script by modifying **Kaaf** (ك). The addition of a distinguishing mark—a small hook or loop—differentiates **Gaf** to represent the "g" sound, which does not exist in Arabic.
- **Usage in Persian and Urdu:** **Gaf** is essential for Persian and Urdu, as many basic words start with a "g" sound, such as "گللاب" (Golāb, meaning "rose") in Persian or "گھر" (Ghar, meaning "house") in Urdu. In Arabic, the closest equivalent is **Qaf** (ق), which produces a much deeper, guttural sound.
- **Symbolism:** **Gaf**'s curved form, much like **Kaaf**, can be seen as a symbol of openness or gathering. In Sufi literature, "g" sounds often introduce concepts related to spiritual journeys and homes (as in **Ghar** or **Gulshan**).

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	گ	گ	گ	گ

Sounds

GĀF is the same as English hard "g" as in "gate".

Hindi equivalent: ग

Connections

GĀF can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final**. The little squiggle over the tail of the letter is not normally written in handwriting.

GĀF has special combination forms with ALIF and LĀM:

ا + گ =	Hindi equivalent: गा
ग = ل + گ	Hindi equivalent: गल or

Remember that nothing can connect after ALIF so is also a breaker. On the other hand is not a breaker because its final element is ل.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
gānā	نغمہ	गाना

gulshan	گلشن	गुलशन
jagānā	جاگو	जगाना
janglī	جنگلی	जंगली

LĀM ل

Laam (ل)

- Historical Origin: Laam comes from the Phoenician Lamed, which symbolized a goad (a tool for guiding livestock).
- Symbolism: Laam is often connected with guidance or direction, much like the original tool it symbolized.

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Additional Examples	ل	ل	ل	ل

Sounds

LĀM is the same as English “l”.

Hindi equivalent: ल

Connections

LĀM can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

LĀM looks similar to ALIF but the two cannot be confused since their connection rules are different.

Compare:

	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
ALIF	ا	Use final	Use detached	ا
LĀM	ل	ل	ل	ل

LĀM has special combination forms with ALIF and KĀF and GĀF:

ا + ل =	Hindi equivalent: ला
क = ل + ک	Hindi equivalent: कल or क्ला
گ = ل + گ	Hindi equivalent: गल or
ک = ا + ل + ک	Hindi equivalent: कला or
گ = ا + ل + گ	Hindi equivalent: गला or

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
lānā	لانے	लाना
kal	کل	कल
gulshan	گلشن	गुलशन
takleef	مسئلہ	तकलीफ
janglī	جنگلی	जंगली
klās	کلاس	क्लास

MEEM م

Meem (م)

- Historical Origin: Meem evolved from Phoenician Mem, symbolizing water.
- Symbolism: Its circular shape is often associated with continuity or life, and in Sufi thought, Meem represents the womb and creation.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
م	MEEM	English "M"	म	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	م	م	م	م
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Connections

MEEM can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

Medial MEEM often looks like a right-pointing kink in the word.

Initial MEEM is often hard to recognize: if there seems to be a slight thickening of ink at the beginning of a word, and if there are no dots above or below, chances are that the word begins with MEEM.

NOON ن

Noon (ن)

Historical Origin: Noon comes from Phoenician Nun, symbolizing a fish.

Symbolism: It represents nourishment or sustenance in mystical thought, reflecting the life-giving properties of water.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ن	NOON	English "N"	न	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	نـ	نـ	نـ	ن
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Sounds

NOON has a special variant, NOON Ghunna, indicating nasalization.

Connections

NOON can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

NOON is a member of the "point system" family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family. For aesthetic reasons the initial form of these letters can assume one of the three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are examples of three different initial shapes of ن:

NOON Ghunna

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ن	NOON Ghunna	Nasal English “N” or “M”	Multiple (fill-in)	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ن	ن	ن	ن
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Sounds

When a nasalized vowel occurs in the middle of a word, followed by a consonant, the nasalization is similar to the English use of “n” or “m” in words like “sing”, “thanks”, “lamp”.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
Hi(n)dī	ہندی	हिन्दी
oo(n)t	اونٹ	ऊँट
tha(n)d	سردی	ठंड
p(ā)nch	پانچ	पांच
ja(n)gal	جنگل	जंगल

At the end of a word, NOON Ghunna is used to nasalize a final long vowel. The pronunciation is similar to French nasalization as in the French words “bon”, “main”, and “lent”. Final NOON Ghunna is analogous to the chandrabindi in Hindi. In its final form, NOON Ghunna looks like regular NOON, but has no dot.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
---------------------------	----------------	------------------

mai(n) nasalized “mai”	میں ہوں	मैं
hoo(n) nasalized “hoo”	میں ہوں	मूँ
hā(n) nasalized “hā”	جی ہاں	हाँ
hai(n) nasalized “hai”	ہے	हैं
thee(n) nasalized “thee”	تھے	थीं

The use of NOON Ghunna is analogous to the use of the bindi and chandrabindi in the Hindi script. Notice that the “chandrabindi” in Hindi looks like a little Urdu (fill-in), and that the nasal dot in Hindi also looks like the medial dot for Urdu (fill-in).

Connections

NOON Ghunna can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

The initial and medial forms of NOON Ghunna are the same as the initial and medial forms of regular NOON. (NOON Ghunna never appears at the beginning of a word, but it appears in initial form after breakers).

Note the special writing rules for the future tense using NOON Ghunna.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
de(n)gay	دے گا	देंगे
le(n)gī	لے جائے گا	लेंगी
hoo(n)gā	کریں گے	हूँगा

VĀO و

Waw (و)

- Historical Origin: Derived from Phoenician Vav, symbolizing a hook or peg.
- Symbolism: Waw represents connection or binding. It's seen as a unifier, as in the conjunction "and" (و).

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
و	VAO	Nasal English "V"	व	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	و	Use Final	Use Detached	و
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Sounds

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
the consonant "v"	vāris	مختلف	व
the long vowel "o" as in "chore"	chor	چور	औ
the long vowel "aw" as in "awful"	daur	چکر	ओ
the long vowel "ū" as in "moon"	angūr	fill-in	fill-in
Notes	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent

At the beginning of a word VĀO always sounds like consonant “v”.	vardī	یکساں	वर्दी
	vatan	ملک	वतन

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
When VĀO comes in the middle or end of a word, it may represent any of the three long vowel sounds or the consonant “v”. Diacritic marks may be used to indicate which sound VĀO represents, but they are usually omitted. The special sign over VĀO indicating the long vowel “ū” is called “ultra pesh”: (fill-in): it is not used in any other context.	lo	لو	लो
	law	لو	fill-in
	loo	لو	लू
	love	محبت	लव
The zabair-zair-pesh signs (fill-in) can be used with VĀO to specify that it is to be read as the consonant “v”. However these marks are usually omitted.	anvar	انور	अनवर
	dilāvar	دلاور	दिलावर
Any word starting with a vowel sound must begin with silent ALIF. So far words beginning with “o”, “aw”, or “ū”, VĀO must be preceded by ALIF:	os	اور	ओर
	awr	اور	और
	ooper	اوپر	ऊपर

Two vowels cannot occur together without an intervening Hamza. So if you ever see two vowel letters in a row, one of them must be functioning as a consonant. Examples:

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
sovay	بونا	सोवे
jāved	جاوید	जावेद
rāvi	راوی	रावी

Special Cases with VĀO

1. In some words borrowed from Persian, VĀO is silent:

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
khāb	خواب	ख़्वाब
khāhish	خواہش	ख़ाहिश

2. Note that VĀO is transliterated into **व** in the Hindi spelling, but it should not be pronounced.
3. In some rare cases, Urdu uses VĀO where Hindi used a short “u” (उ):

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
khush	خوش	खुश
khud	خود	खुद
dukān	دکان	दुकान
Madhubālā	مدھوبالا	मधुबाला
Hanumān	ہنومان	हनुमान

4. While some Hindi and Sanskrit words end with a short “u” (उ), Urdu words cannot end with a short vowel. When transliterating such words from Hindi to Urdu, use a VĀO at the end.

Connections

VĀO can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final**.

VĀO is a breaker: no letter can be connected after it. Thus VĀO has only two forms: a detached and a final form:

When V̄AO appears at the beginning of a word, it will be in its detached form.	vatan	ملک
When V̄AO appears after another breaker, it will be in its detached form.	do	دو
When V̄AO appears after a non-breaker, it will be in its final form.	sonā	سونا

HAY

Haa (ہ)

- Historical Origin: Like Haa (ح), this form evolved from the same root but developed differently in Arabic script.
- Symbolism: This "h" sound, especially at the end of words, often represents a soft closure or finality, especially in proper nouns.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ہ	HAY	English "H"	ह	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	~	‡	‡	ہ
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Sounds

HAY is one of the TWO "h" sounds in Urdu. Both sound the same. However, you must learn when to use each one. They are not interchangeable.

We call ہ the Hindi HAY to distinguish it from Arabic HAY ح.

In many cases, when ہ occurs at the end of a word following a consonant, it sounds like a final ALIF. In fact, most nouns (including proper nouns) ending in a long "a" sound should be spelled with ہ at the end instead of final ALIF. This is similar to the final "h" in English names like Sarah and Deborah.

Examples: (fill-in)

Connections

HAY can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

The little inverted comma below the medial form of HAY is sometimes omitted.

Initial HAY takes slightly different forms depending on the following letter. With most letters it has a tiny hook shape. Before ALIF and letters in the point system family, it just a single cusp. No matter what its shape, the initial form always has the small comma underneath.

Do Chashmi HAY

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ھ	Do Chashmi HAY	Aspirated English “H”	हृ	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	ھ	ھ	ھ	ھ
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Sounds

Do Chashmi HAY (“two-eyed HAY”) is used to indicate aspiration. Urdu has a set of consonants that are aspirated, i.e. pronounced with an extra puff of air. When Do Chashmi HAY follows a consonant, that consonant should be aspirated. Hold your hand up in front of your mouth. You should feel a puff of air when you pronounce an aspirated consonant.

Do Chashmi HAY is also occasionally encountered as a substitute for Hindi HAY (हृ). Here is a list of all the aspirated consonants in Urdu. Note that not every Urdu consonant has an aspirated version.

	Example (transliteration)	Hindi Equivalent(Urdu)	Notes
fill-in	“bh”	भ	
fill-in	“ph”	फ	Do not confuse with ف
fill-in	dental “th”	थ	
fill-in	retroflex “th”	ठ	
fill-in	“jh”	झ	
fill-in	“chh”	छ	

fill-in	dental "dh"	ध	
fill-in	retroflex "dh"	ढ	
fill-in	retroflex flap "rh"	ढ़	
fill-in	"kh"	ख	Do not confuse with ख़
fill-in	"gh"	घ	Do not confuse with ग़

A few words that end with an aspirated consonant in Hindi end with an unaspirated version of that consonant in Urdu.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
bhook	زلزلہ	भूक
jhoot	جھوٹ	झूठ
hont	ہونٹ	होंठ

Connections

Do Chashmi HAY can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

Do Chashmi HAY will not be found as the first letter of a word unless it is substituting for regular Hindi HAY (rare).

Hamza

Hamza (ء)

- Historical Origin: A later addition to represent a glottal stop.
- Symbolism: Hamza often represents a pause or an interruption in sound, symbolizing reflection or transition.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ء	Hamza	Vowel Separator	N/A	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	No Final Form	ئ	ئ	ء
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Hamza functions as a vowel separator. It has no sounds of its own.

Connections

Occasionally two vowels occur together in a word without an intervening consonant. In such cases Hamza is inserted to carry the second vowel. The first vowel can be long or short. For example:

لِ اَ	fill-in	<-	fill-in
گَ اَ	fill-in	<-	fill-in
نَ اِ	fill-in	<-	fill-in
جَ اِ	fill-in	<-	fill-in

On a detached و (VĀO) Hamza is put directly on top of the و without any cusp.

For example	خَ اِ = fill-in	گَ اِ = fill-in	اَ اِ = fill-in
-------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------

But a final form (connected) VĀO needs an additional cusp for Hamza:

گَ اِ =

Chotti YAY

Ya (ی)

- Historical Origin: Derived from Phoenician Yodh, symbolizing a hand.
- Symbolism: It symbolizes effort or creation, as the hand is often a symbol of action.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound				Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
ی	Chotti YAY	Consonant “y” and long vowel sound “ee”				य and ई	Teacher Icon
		Final	Medial	Initial	Detached		
Basic Forms		fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	ی		
In Context		fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in		
Write in Context		fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in		

Sounds

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
the consonant “y”	yār	fill-in	य
the long vowel “ee” as in “green”	teen	fill-in	ई

Special Note:

While some Hindi and Sanskrit words end with a short “i” (ई), Urdu words cannot end with a short vowel. When transliterating such words from Hindi to Urdu, use a Chhoti YAY at the end.

Connections

Chhoti YAY can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached**, **initial**, **medial**, and **final**.

Chhoti YAY is a member of the “point system” family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family. For aesthetic reasons the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are examples of three different initial shapes of ۷:

fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
---------	---------	---------

Compare the shape of final after various letters:

Fill-in

Chhoti YAY and Badi YAY look the **same** in their initial and medial forms. Only their final forms look different. See the notes on Badi YAY. Sometimes a small vertical diacritical mark is placed below medial YAY to indicate that it is Chhoti YAY as opposed to Badi YAY, but this mark is usually omitted:

Līlā	fill-in	लीला
------	---------	------

Remember, any word starting with vowel sound must begin with the dummy consonant ALIF. So for words beginning with (“ee”), Chhoti YAY must be preceded by ALIF:

eemān	fill-in	ईमान
-------	---------	------

Badi YAY

YAA (اے)

- Historical Origin: A variant of Chhoti Yay, distinguished for vowel sounds.
- Symbolism: It often symbolizes extension or completion, particularly at the end of words.

Urdu Letter	Letter Name	Sound	Hindi Equivalent	Teacher
اے	Badi YAY	Long vowel “a”	ए and ऐ	Teacher Icon
	Final	Medial	Initial	Detached
Basic Forms	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	اے
In Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
Write in Context	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in	fill-in

Sounds

Badi YAY (“Big YAY”) can represent two different vowel sounds:

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
a long vowel sound like Spanish ‘e’ or the “a” in the English word “say” (often transliterated as “e” but we use “ay” at the end of a word)	se (say)	اے	ए
a long vowel sound like the “a” in the English word “dad” (usually transliterated as “ai”)	kaisā	fill-in	ऐ

Special Note:

When Badi YAY comes at the end of a word, it can represent either of the two long vowel sounds “ay” or “ai”.

Sound	Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
Chhoti YAY and Badi YAY look the same in their initial and medial forms. Only their final forms look different. So when YAY comes in the middle of a word, it can represent any of the three long vowel sounds “e”, “ai”, or “ee”. Diacritic marks may be used to indicate which sound YAY represents, but these are usually omitted. The special sign under initial or medial YAY indicates the long vowel “ee” (Chhoti YAY). This sign is not used in any other context.	“lenā”	fill-in	लेना
	“Lailā”	fill-in	लैला
	“Lilā” (Leela)	fill-in	लीला
Remember, any word starting with a vowel sound must begin with ALIF. So for words beginning with “e” or “ai”, Badi YAY must be preceded by ALIF:	“ek” (Leela)	fill-in	एक
	“aisā” (Leela)	fill-in	ऐसा

Two vowels cannot come together without an intervening Hamza. So if you see YAY followed by itself or another vowel letter, then it must be the consonant “y”.

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
jiyā	fill-in	जिया
jiyo	fill-in	जियो

Special Cases:

Hindi words ending in **य** should be transliterated into Urdu with final Badi YAY:

Example (transliteration)	Example (Urdu)	Hindi Equivalent
---------------------------	----------------	------------------

gāay (gai)	fill-in	गाय
chāay (chai)	fill-in	चाय
Akshay	fill-in	अक्षय
samay	fill-in	समय

Connections

Badi YAY can connect from both sides: Thus it has four forms: **detached, initial, medial, and final.**

Badi YAY is a member of the “point system” family. The letters in this family consist only of a point or cusp in their initial and medial forms. Dots or symbols above or below the cusp differentiate the members of this family. For aesthetic reasons the initial form of these letters can assume one of three slightly different shapes depending on which letter follows. The use of these three different shapes will come naturally with experience. Here are examples of three different initial shapes of ے:

fill-in	fill-in	fill-in
---------	---------	---------

Chhoti YAY and Badi YAY look the same in their initial and medial forms. Only their final and detached forms look different.

Alphabet Table

SL. No.	Urdu Letter	Hindi Equivalent	English Sound	Example Word
1	ا (Alif)	अ (A)	A (Letter: Alif)	الله / اﻟﻠﻮﻩ / Allah
2	ب (Bay)	ब (Ba)	B (Letter: Bay)	بادل / बादل / Baadal (Cloud)
3	پ (Pay)	प (Pa)	P (Letter: Pay)	پتنگ / پتنگ / Patang (Kite)
4	ت (Tay)	त (Ta)	T (Letter: Tay)	تختی / تختی / Takhti (Board)
5	ٹ (Ttay)	ट (Ta)	Tt (Letter: Ttay)	ٹماٹر / टमाटर / Tamatar (Tomato)
6	ث (Say)	स (Sa)	S (Letter: Say)	ثواب / سوااب / Sawaab (Reward)
7	ج (Jeem)	ज (Ja)	J (Letter: Jeem)	جان / جان / Jaan (Life)
8	چ (Chay)	च (Cha)	Ch (Letter: Chay)	چاند / चांद / Chaand (Moon)
9	ح (Hay)	ह (Ha)	H (Letter: Hay)	حیات / हयात / Hayaat (Life)
10	خ (Khaa)	ख (Kha)	Kh (Letter: Khaa)	خواب / خواب / Khwaab (Dream)
11	د (Dal)	द (Da)	D (Letter: Dal)	دن / दिन / Din (Day)
12	ڈ (Ddal)	ड (Da)	Dd (Letter: Ddal)	ڈبہ / डिब्बा / Dabba (Box)
13	ذ (Zaal)	ज़ (Za)	Z (Letter: Zaal)	ذکر / ذکر / Zikr (Remembrance)
14	ر (Ray)	र (Ra)	R (Letter: Ray)	راستہ / रास्ता / Raasta (Path)
15	ڑ (Rray)	ड़ (Rra)	Rr (Letter: Rray)	لڑکا / लड़का / Ladka (Boy)
16	ز (Zay)	ज़ (Za)	Z (Letter: Zay)	زمانہ / जमाना / Zamana (Era)
17	ژ (Zhay)	झ (Jha)	Zh (Letter: Zhay)	ژالہ / झाला / Zhalla (Hailstorm)
18	س (Seen)	स (Sa)	S (Letter: Seen)	سوال / سوال / Sawaal (Question)
19	ش (Sheen)	श (Sha)	Sh (Letter: Sheen)	شمع / शमा / Shama (Candle)
20	ص (Saad)	स (Sa)	S (Letter: Saad)	صبر / सब्र / Sabr (Patience)

SL. No.	Urdu Letter	Hindi Equivalent	English Sound	Example Word
21	ض (Zaad)	ज़ (Za)	Z (Letter: Zaad)	ضمير / ज़मीर / Zameer (Conscience)
22	ط (T'oy)	त (Ta)	T (Letter: T'oy)	طوفان / तूफान / Toofaan (Storm)
23	ظ (Zoy)	ज़ (Za)	Z (Letter: Zoy)	ظلم / जुल्म / Zulm (Oppression)
24	ع (Ain)	अ (A)	A (Letter: Ain)	عشق / इश्क़ / Ishq (Love)
25	غ (Ghayn)	ग़ (Gha)	Gh (Letter: Ghayn)	غم / ग़म / Gham (Sorrow)
26	ف (Fay)	फ़ (Fa)	F (Letter: Fay)	فصل / फसल / Fasal (Crop)
27	ق (Qaaf)	क (Ka)	Q (Letter: Qaaf)	قلب / क़لب / Qalb (Heart)
28	ک (Kaaf)	क (Ka)	K (Letter: Kaaf)	کتاب / किताब / Kitaab (Book)
29	گ (Gaaf)	ग (Ga)	G (Letter: Gaaf)	گانا / गाना / Gaana (Song)
30	ل (Laam)	ल (La)	L (Letter: Laam)	لہر / लहर / Lehar (Wave)
31	م (Meem)	म (Ma)	M (Letter: Meem)	محبت / मोहब्बत / Mohabbat (Love)
32	ن (Noon)	न (Na)	N (Letter: Noon)	نماز / नमाज़ / Namaaz (Prayer)
33	ں (Noon Ghunna)	ं (Anuswaar)	Ng (Letter: Noon Ghunna)	گنگا / गंगा / Ganga (River)
34	و (Waw)	व (Va)	W (Letter: Waw)	وقت / वक्त / Waqt (Time)
35	ہ (Haa)	ह (Ha)	H (Letter: Haa)	ہوا / हवा / Hawa (Air)
36	ہ (Do Chashmi Hay)	ह (Ha)	Hh (Letter: Do Chashmi Hay)	یہاں / यहाँ / Yahaan (Here)
37	ء (Hamza)	(None)	' (Letter: Hamza)	مسئول / مس'ؤول / Mas'ool (Responsible)
38	ی (Yay)	य (Ya)	Y (Letter: Yay)	یار / यार / Yaar (Friend)
39	ے (Badi Yay)	ए (E)	E (Letter: Badi Yay)	بڑے / बड़े / Bade (Big)

Conclusion:

The Urdu alphabet stands as a profound confluence of culture, history, and linguistic precision. It is a script that has carried the voice of poets, philosophers, and the common people across centuries. Each letter in the Urdu script is more than a sound or a symbol—it is a gateway to understanding the intellectual, emotional, and spiritual fabric of the Indo-Persian world.

At its core, language serves as the most direct manifestation of human thought and emotion, and the Urdu script—rooted in Arabic, Persian, and Indian dialects—encapsulates this universal truth. The evolution of each letter, from its Phoenician origins to its place in the subcontinent, reflects a scientific and cultural journey shaped by geography, empire, and literature. The use of Alif, the first letter, for example, speaks not only to the linguistic structure of Urdu but to the philosophical concepts of unity and existence. Alif's tall, singular form mirrors the oneness of the divine, a recurring theme in the mystical poetry of Ghalib and Iqbal, where the script and its sounds become metaphors for universal truths.

The intricate orthography of Urdu is a testament to its scientific precision. Each letter represents a specific phoneme, and yet, like all great linguistic systems, Urdu goes beyond mere functionality. The relationship between sound and meaning in this script reveals the philosophical depth of language itself—how letters and words transcend the boundaries of the page to evoke the deepest of human emotions. In Bay (ب), for instance, we do not only see a "B" sound; we see the beginning of blessings, as in the word Bismillah. The script here operates on multiple levels, invoking not only sound but also spiritual and cultural resonance.

The blending of script and phonetics in the Urdu alphabet also reflects a harmonious balance between the intellectual and aesthetic. As this research has shown, each letter is not only defined by its phonetic properties but by its visual poetry. Jeem (ج), for instance, with its graceful curves, reflects the journey of human life—used in words such as Jaan (life) or Jannah (paradise). In this way, the Urdu script mirrors the delicate balance between beauty and meaning, much like the ghazals and couplets for which it is most famously used.

From a linguistic standpoint, the Urdu script has been meticulously designed to capture the full range of human expression. The distinction between letters like Zaad (ض) and Zay (ز) may seem subtle, but each carries its own historical weight and phonetic nuance. These letters are essential in preserving the integrity of the language, where a slight change in pronunciation can alter the emotional tone or spiritual meaning of a word. In many ways, the script is a scientific puzzle, with each letter being a piece that fits into a larger, more complex linguistic system. But as much as it is grounded in science, it is equally embedded in cultural practice.

Philosophically, the Urdu alphabet represents the eternal human quest for expression, meaning, and connection. The script is a reflection of socio-political histories, spiritual inquiries, and artistic ambitions that have shaped South Asia for centuries. Urdu's letters, sounds, and structures are the living embodiments of stories and traditions passed down through generations. In poetry, the rhyme and meter of Urdu become a dance of words that speak to both the intellect and the heart, creating a symphony of human experience.

This research, in presenting the phonetic equivalence of Urdu with Hindi and English, serves to demystify the Urdu script for a broader audience, while celebrating its inherent complexity. By exploring the alphabet through a lens of science and art, we uncover the multi-dimensional nature of language: as a tool for communication, as an artistic medium, and as a philosophical inquiry into the human condition. Urdu letters are not merely written forms but vessels for poetry, spirituality, and identity.

The ultimate goal of this work has been to open a door to the mystical beauty of Urdu, while making its complex system accessible to learners. For non-Urdu speakers, understanding the letters offers a chance to engage with one of the richest literary traditions in the world. For Urdu speakers, it is a reminder of the depth of their linguistic heritage. Urdu poetry, with its delicate use of Bahr, Qaafiya, and Radeef, finds its roots in the very script this paper explores. In each letter, there is a story, a history, and a sound that transcends time and space.

The beauty of the Urdu script lies not just in the sounds it represents but in the cultural tapestry it weaves—uniting nations, histories, and souls. As learners and admirers of this language, we are not only mastering a script but becoming part of a legacy that celebrates both the intellectual rigor and the emotional depth of human expression.